

**LEGAL BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN THE NEW
UZBEKISTAN.**

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Annotation: The article presents the legal basis of the laws adopted today in our national legislation on international relations and protection of human rights. Also, the adoption of the "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" by the UNESCO organization has a role in ensuring international relations. The essence of the reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan to ensure inter-national harmony has been explained.

Key words: Nation, Declaration of Human Rights, UNESCO, Democracy, UN, Ombudsman, Convention, Oliy Majlis, OSCE, Paris Charter.

**YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLATLARARO MUNOSABATLARNING
HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.**

Annotatsiya: Maqola Bugungi kunda milliy qonunchiligimizda Millatlararo munosabatlar va inson huquqlari himoya qilish borasida qabul qilinayotgan qonunlarni huquqiy asoslari keltirilgan. Shuningdek YUNESKO tashkiloti tomonidan "Bag'rikenglik tamoyillari deklaratsiyasini" qabul qilinishi Millatlararo munosabatlarni taminlashdagi o'rni. Yangi O'zbekistonda Millatlararo totuvlikni taminlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar mohiyati yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Millat, Inson huquqlari deklaratsiyasi, YUNESKO, Demokratiya, BMT, Ombudsman, Konvensiya, Oliy Majlis, YXHT, Parij hartiyasi.

ПРАВОВАЯ ОСНОВА МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.

Аннотация: В статье представлена правовая основа принимаемых сегодня законов в нашем национальном законодательстве о международных отношениях и защите прав человека. Также принятие «Декларации принципов толерантности» организацией ЮНЕСКО играет роль в обеспечении международных отношений. Разъяснена суть реформ, проводимых в новом Узбекистане для обеспечения межнационального согласия.

Ключевые слова: нация, Декларация прав человека, ЮНЕСКО, демократия, ООН, Омбудсмен, Конвенция, Олий Мажлис, ОБСЕ, Парижская хартия.

In the new Uzbekistan, democratic values were defined as the highest values for our society. Among them - "Universal values such as human rights and democracy fully correspond to the interests of the national statehood of our Republic" [1.78,79]. At the core of the Constitution of independent Uzbekistan is the goal of establishing a humane, democratic, legal state based on the general rules of international law. One of the main conditions for the establishment of a democratic-legal state is to observe human rights and ensure their legal protection. In particular, the legal basis for the protection of the interests and rights of representatives of different nationalities living in the territory of our republic was created, and every citizen had the opportunity to enjoy equal rights, regardless of their nationality, religion and political beliefs. In this sense, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it must be recognized, embodies all the internationally recognized basic norms of respect and observance of human rights, that citizens have the same rights and freedoms, regardless of their social origin. ensures and guarantees equality before the law. After all, as stated in Article 8 of our

Basic Law, the people of Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality, are citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The concept of "people of Uzbekistan" serves as a moral basis for mutual respect, friendship and solidarity between people of different nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country and working towards a common goal.

As stated in Article 4 of our dictionary, "The Republic of Uzbekistan ensures respect for the languages, customs and traditions of all nations and peoples living in its territory, and creates conditions for their development." The rational policy of Uzbekistan in this regard is of great importance in the implementation of national ideas such as the development of the homeland, peace of the country, and the well-being of the people as a partner and in harmony with all our compatriots. Not only our national laws, but also international treaties on human rights are important in the implementation of human rights protection. It is worth mentioning that our Constitution declared the primacy of international law and joined more than 70 international documents aimed at strengthening and protecting the rights of various categories of citizens (women, children, disabled people, ethnic groups) and human rights in its territory. and the necessary organizational and legal foundations and guarantees for the promotion and protection of human rights have been formed, as well as the organizational mechanism for the promotion and protection of human rights, as well as the corresponding infrastructure.

According to the recommendations of the United Nations, the following national human rights institutions have been created and are working in Uzbekistan:

1. Representative of the Oliy Majlis on human rights (ombudsman) (1995).
2. The Institute for Monitoring Current Legislation under the President (2005) (initially under the Oliy Majlis in 1996).
3. National Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Human Rights (1996). The ideological basis of the center's activity program is the universal principles of legal culture development stated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Documents aimed at protecting human rights are of great importance in the formation and development of this field. The role of international documents on human rights is also

determined by the fact that they embody legal norms that serve the interests of the world. To date, many international documents have been adopted for the sake of human interests, and they have a universal and regional character. In particular, there are about 80 international human rights treaties and conventions signed by the UN General Assembly, more than 160 by the Council of Europe, more than 70 by UNESCO, more than 30 by the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, and many international human rights treaties and conventions by various regional international organizations (Latin contract, agreement), declarations (Lat. statement, announcement), pacts were accepted. Currently, there are about 500 international documents on human rights. These international documents set the world standards for human rights and the principle of their precedence over national laws is recognized by most countries. International treaties on human rights to which the Republic of Uzbekistan has joined. To date, our republic has signed more than 70 international documents on human rights. These international documents serve as the main criteria for the adoption of laws and regulations aimed at protecting human rights and freedoms in our country. International documents on the protection of human rights to which the Republic of Uzbekistan has joined can also be classified separately. International agreements to which our country has joined can be divided into three groups. The first group covers universal and regional international agreements on human rights that are valid under normal conditions of peace and tranquility. These documents include the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted on December 10, 1948, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, adopted in 1966, and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and Additional Protocol I. , we can list documents such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child adopted in 1989[2.2]. The second group consists of international legal documents of the International Labor Organization. Most of the international documents adopted by the ILO focus on the protection of economic and social rights related to labor relations. These documents include: 1935 Reduction of Working Hours to 40 Hours Convention 47, 1936 Annual Leave Convention 52, etc.[3.3]. The third group consists of a series

of documents that are quite extensive in terms of content and volume, and include international documents on the observance of human rights during armed conflicts. In this place, in particular, the four adopted on August 12, 1949 - On the relief of the condition of the wounded and sick in the armed forces in action, On the relief of the condition of the wounded, sick and shipwrecked members of the armed forces at sea Geneva Conventions on the Treatment of Prisoners of War and the Protection of the Civilian Population in Time of War, as well as two Additional Protocols signed in 1977 (an official written statement on an issue, a document)– We are talking about Protocol I for the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts and Protocol II for the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts. In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan joined the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1992. The relevant clauses of the declaration are 18, 25, 26, 29, 30, 32, 33, 34, 37, 39, 41, 57 of the Constitution (equal rights of people, civil rights, freedom of speech, opinion, political rights, work, rest , education), reflected in the relevant articles of the Criminal Codes. In 1995, it ratified the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination and adopted the Durban Declaration, the Program of Action and the Final Document adopted at the Durban Conference in order to create the necessary conditions for ensuring the rights of representatives of every nationality and people living in the country. fully supported. In 1997, he joined the declaration on ending all forms of discrimination based on religion and belief [4.22-23]. The "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" was adopted by the UN UNESCO organization in 1995. Another international document related to the protection of human rights is the Paris Charter for a New Europe. This document was adopted by the OSCE member states in Paris on November 21, 1990, and the Republic of Uzbekistan signed it on November 27, 1993 in Paris. According to the Charter of Paris for New Europe, the Republic of Uzbekistan undertakes to observe the rights ensuring the equality of every person, to develop democracy, to realize the basic rights and freedoms of the individual and other obligations.

The Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in its 2nd session held on May 6, 1995, decided to join a number of international documents on the protection of human rights. These international instruments include: Convention 47 on Limitation of Working Hours to 40 Hours per Week, adopted at Geneva on June 21, 1935, Annual Leave with Pay Convention, adopted at Geneva on June 24, 1936 Convention 52, adopted at Geneva, 1919, revised on June 28, 1952, Convention 103 on Maternity Protection, adopted at Geneva, July 9, 1964, Convention on Employment Policy, 1974 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, adopted in New York on December 18. In accordance with these international documents, Uzbekistan must comply with the principle of not exceeding 40 hours of working time, ensure the right of every working citizen to take a paid vacation of not less than 6 days a year, and allow women to give birth before 12 weeks of pregnancy. To give a language, to allocate a sufficient amount of money to a woman for herself and her child, to ensure the right of each person to freely choose a profession depending on his specialty, to observe the principle of equality between men and women, to reflect this principle in the Constitution and laws, in relation to women undertakes to take measures to prohibit various restrictions. A lot of work is being done in our country in connection with the implementation of international agreements to which our republic has joined. In this regard, the activities carried out in connection with the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Convention on the Elimination of Any Discrimination Against Women are particularly noteworthy. However, there are a number of shortcomings in fulfilling the requirements of some international agreements. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the period of fundamental reforms has begun in New Uzbekistan since 2016. In particular, it is a fact that the President's decree on the "Strategy of Actions" was signed on February 7, 2017, as a result of the work carried out on inter-ethnic relations with the initiatives of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Point 5 of the strategy of actions is to ensure security, inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, to strengthen the independence and sovereignty of our country aimed at conducting a deeply thought-out, mutually

beneficial and practical foreign policy, security in the vicinity of Uzbekistan, creation of stable and harmonious neighborhood environment, strengthening of the international prestige of our country, directly dedicated to inter-ethnic relations. Decree No. PF-5046 dated May 19, 2017 "On measures to further improve inter-ethnic relations and friendly relations with foreign countries" and on this basis "Inter-ethnic relations and foreign relations under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan The adoption of the Decision No. PQ-2993 "On the organization of the activities of the Committee of friendly relations with other countries" brought the inter-ethnic relations to a new stage in New Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that new ideas and initiatives aimed at further strengthening inter-ethnic and inter-civilian harmony are emerging in our country, which will serve to strengthen the fortress of friendship in the literal sense. As the head of our state admitted, "Uzbekistan has a lot of wealth, but our greatest wealth, our highest value is the peace, inter-ethnic friendship and solidarity that reign in our society."

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